

Cyclodimerization of 1,1-dicyanoalkenes and arylidenecyanoacetates promoted by ytterbium diiodide

W. K. Su* and B. B. Yang

College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Zhejiang University of Technology, Hangzhou, Zhejiang, 310014, P. R. China

E-mail : suweike@zjut.edu.cn biboyang@zjut.edu.cn

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The reductive cyclodimerization of 1,1-dicyanoalkenes and arylidenecyanoacetates promoted by YbI_2 has been studied. Functionalized cyclopentenes are obtained in both high yields and stereoselectivity.

The chemistry of samarium diiodide (SmI_2) is of current interest in organic synthesis. SmI_2 has been developed as a mild, neutral and ether-soluble one-electron transfer reductant and there have been many examples of its use in the reduction or reductive coupling of various functional groups¹. However, there are only a few reports on the utility of ytterbium diiodide in organic synthesis². Utilization of the corresponding ytterbium diiodide has lagged behind mainly because the preparation of ytterbium diiodide by reaction of ytterbium with 1,2-diiodoethane requires a reaction time of over 2 days and ytterbium diiodide has limiting solubility of $<0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in solvents like THF. In our previous work, we achieved a facile preparation of ytterbium diiodide by the reaction of ytterbium metal with iodine in THF³.

Here we wish to report the reductive cyclodimerization of 1,1-dicyanoalkenes and arylidenecyanoacetates promoted by YbI_2 to afford functionalized cyclopentenes in both high yields and stereoselectivity (Scheme 1). 1,1-Dicyanoalkenes and arylidenecyanoacetates have enough

coupling cyclization product is isolated. Probably this result may be attributed to the low stability of the radical anion intermediates⁴.

Table 1. YbI_2 promoted cyclodimerization of 1,1-dicyanoalkenes and arylidenecyanoacetates

Compd. entry	Ar	EWG	Time (min)	Yield (%)
a	C_6H_5	CN	5	86
b	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$	CN	5	82
c	2-Furyl	CN	10	85
d	2-Thiophenyl	CN	10	81
e	3-Thiophenyl	CN	10	84
f	$p\text{-Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4$	CO_2CH_3	5	80
g	$m\text{-Br.C}_6\text{H}_5$	$\text{CO}_2\text{Pr-t}$	5	77
h	2-Furyl	$\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	15	79
i	2-Thiophenyl	$\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	15	80
j	3-Thiophenyl	$\text{CO}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$	15	81

*Isolated yields.

Scheme 1

reactivity to complete the reductive cyclodimerization in the presence of ytterbium diiodide due to their carbon-carbon double bonds being activated by attached electron-withdrawing cyano and alkoxy carbonyl groups and the stability of five-membered ring products. The results are summarized in Table 1. Unfortunately, when substrates are derived from aliphatic aldehydes or ketones, no reductive

It is found in our present work that β,β -diphenyl-activated olefins react with ytterbium diiodide in THF/MeOH to give the corresponding saturated derivatives (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Experimental

Metallic ytterbium, aldehydes, malononitrile, alkyl cyanoacetates and all solvents used were of commercial grade. 1,1-Dicyanoalkenes, arylidenecyanoacetates and

β,β -diphenyl-activated olefins were synthesized by the reaction of carbonyl compounds and malononitrile, alkyl cyanoacetates following the usual procedure⁶. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium/benzophenone immediately before use. All reactions were carried out under dry nitrogen atmosphere. M.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC-400 instrument downfield from internal tetramethylsilane and mass spectra on a HP 5989B spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument.

Ytterbium powder (0.173 g, 1 mmol) was dried at room temperature under a stream of nitrogen. One drop of methyl iodine was added to it and heated slightly by a heat gun to activate the Yb metal. THF (30 ml) and iodine (0.254 g, 1 mmol) were then added to it at room temperature. The mixture was magnetically stirred for 2 h and a light yellow green solution of YbI₂ was obtained. Then 1,1-dicyanoalkenes or arylidenecyanoacetates (1 mmol in 3 ml THF) was added (as for β,β -diphenyl-activated olefins : 0.5 mmol in 3 ml THF followed by 3 ml MeOH) to it. The reaction was complete within a few minutes. The products were treated with 0.1 M HCl (5 ml) and then extracted with diethyl ether (3 × 30 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with brine and dried over anhyd. MgSO₄. After the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, the crude products were purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (1 : 3) as eluent : **2a**, m.p. 128~129° (lit.^{4a} 128~130°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3380, 3200, 2210, 1670, 1630, 1505; δ_{H} 3.84 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.60 (1H, d, ArCH), 5.20 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.11~7.70 (10H, m, ArH); **2b**, 96~98° (lit.^{4a} 95~97°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3382, 3240, 2211, 1670, 1620, 1520; δ_{H} 3.66 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.17 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.55 (1H, d, ArCH), 5.46 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.77~7.50 (8H, m, ArH); **2c**, 123~126° (lit.^{4a} 125~127°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3366, 3242, 2210, 1679, 1630, 1510; δ_{H} 4.23 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.62 (1H, d, ArCH), 5.65 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.29~7.55 (6H, m, ArH); **2d**, 129~130° (Found : C, 59.74; H, 3.21; N, 17.44. C₁₆H₁₀N₄S₂ requires : C, 59.63; H, 3.11; N, 17.39%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3368, 3240, 2210, 1680, 1620, 1506; δ_{H} 4.27 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.74 (1H, d, ArCH), 5.33 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.92~7.91 (6H, m, ArH); m/z 324 (M⁺ + 2, 3), 323 (M⁺ + 1, 5), 322 (M⁺, 19), 321 (7), 289 (3), 162 (22), 161 (33), 160 (100), 149 (56), 83 (11), 82 (11), 81 (9); **2e**, 133~135° (Found : C, 59.64; H, 3.16; N, 17.33. C₁₆H₁₀N₄S₂ requires : C, 59.63; H, 3.11; N, 17.39%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3362, 3240, 2210, 1680, 1622, 1506; δ_{H} 3.98 (1H, d, ArCH), 4.62 (1H, d, ArCH), 5.28 (2H, br s, NH₂),

6.90~7.45 (6H, m, ArH); m/z 323 (M⁺ + 1, 12), 322 (M⁺, 36), 321 (15), 289 (26), 162 (26), 161 (37), 149 (100), 85 (23), 84 (30), 83 (21); **2f** 174~176° (Found : C, 59.48; H, 4.11; N, 6.21. C₂₂H₁₈C₁₂N₂O₄ requires : C, 59.34; H, 4.07; N, 6.29%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3450, 3350, 2250, 1760, 1685, 1645, 1575, 1500, 1450, 1300, 1220, 1090, 1015, 820; δ_{H} 3.39 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.72 (1H, d, CH), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.30 (1H, d, CH), 5.94 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.94~7.30 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 448 (M⁺ + 4, 15), 446 (M⁺ + 2, 72), 444 (M⁺, 100), 443 (M⁺ - 1, 29), 413 (43), 388 (12), 386 (62), 384 (94), 352 (72), 324 (58), 288 (37), 255 (32), 215 (27), 189 (37), 164 (61), 155 (37); **2g**, 130~132° (Found : C, 52.81; H, 4.53; N, 4.79. C₂₆H₂₆Br₂N₂O₄ requires : C, 52.90; H, 4.44; N, 4.74%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3450, 3360, 3280, 3000, 2250, 1750, 1685, 1650, 1580, 1480, 1380, 1275, 1100; δ_{H} 0.73 (3H, d, CH₃) 1.10 (3H, d, CH₃), 1.30 (3H, d, CH₃), 1.36 (3H, d, CH₃), 3.93 (1H, d, CH), 4.36 (1H, d, CH), 4.90 (1H, m, OCH), 5.20 (1H, m, OCH), 6.07 (2H, br s, NH₂), 7.00~7.80 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 592 (M⁺ + 4, 2), 590 (M⁺ + 2, 4), 580 (M⁺, 2), 547 (8), 505 (10), 503 (16), 461 (15), 208 (12), 171 (22), 169 (23), 43 (100); **2h**, 133~135° (lit.^{4d} 131~133°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3408, 3327, 3210, 2983, 2938, 2902, 2875, 2247, 1743, 1677, 1633, 1583, 1465; δ_{H} 0.80 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.26 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.75~4.18 (3H, m, CH₂ and CH), 4.28~4.50 (3H, m, CH₂ and CH), 5.98 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.19~7.55 (6H, m, ArH); **2i**, 138~139° (Found : C, 57.72; H, 4.80; N, 5.75. C₂₀H₂₀N₂O₄S₂ requires : C, 57.69; H, 4.81; N, 5.77%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3420, 3322, 3205, 2980, 2938, 2900, 2876, 2248, 1746, 1677, 1630, 1582, 1469; δ_{H} 0.95 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.25 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.86 (1H, d, CH), 4.08 (2H, dd, CH₂), 4.27 (2H, dd, CH₂), 4.74 (1H, d, CH), 5.36 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.93~7.53 (6H, m, ArH); m/z 417 (M⁺ + 1, 11), 416 (M⁺, 37), 387 (6), 370 (17), 343 (31), 324 (15), 298 (18), 297 (39), 269 (26), 187 (14), 149 (63), 142 (27), 141 (32), 137 (39), 136 (69), 97 (82), 86 (59), 84 (100); **2j**, 144~146° (Found : C, 57.77; H, 4.89; N, 5.70. C₂₀H₂₀N₂O₄S₂ requires : C, 57.69; H, 4.81; N, 5.77%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3420, 3326, 3200, 2980, 2938, 2900, 2876, 2248, 1746, 1678, 1630, 1580, 1472; δ_{H} 1.00 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.30 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.96 (1H, d, CH), 4.10 (2H, dd, CH₂), 4.32 (2H, dd, CH₂), 4.61 (1H, d, CH), 5.96 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.80~7.50 (6H, m, ArH); m/z 418 (M⁺ + 2, 13), 417 (M⁺ + 1, 26), 416 (M⁺, 100), 414 (12), 387 (10), 370 (13), 343 (31), 324 (14), 298 (25), 297 (65), 269 (40), 187 (16), 149 (33), 141 (12), 137 (39), 136 (69), 97 (25), 85 (20), 84 (10); **4a**, 80~81° (lit.⁵ 79~80°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2930, 2896, 2262, 1580, 768; δ_{H} 4.40 (1H, d, CH), 4.60 (1H, d, CH), 7.12~7.66 (10H, m, ArH); **4b**,

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76~77° (lit⁵ 75~77°), $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 2932, 2886, 2860, 2254, 1728, 1580, 1290, 1108, 756, δ_{H} 1.05 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.06 (2H, q, CH₂), 4.20 (1H, d, CH), 4.70 (1H, d, CH), 6.90~7.31 (10H, m, ArH)

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